

Schemes and Strategies for Women Empowerment in India

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Bhavani, A. "Schemes and Strategies for Women Empowerment in India." *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 14–17.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2551318>

Dr.A.Bhavani

*Assistant Professor, Department of History
E.M.G. Yadava Women's College, Madurai*

Abstract

Women Empowerment is the process of treating the women with same status with that of men in all the fields of the society. Women Empowerment has become a movement now but in our country it only seems a distant dream. Now the basic problem of a women faces is that of education, poverty and safety and health. In order tackle it various schemes and policies are drafted and implemented. Thus the paper concludes with the positive note that with all the required tools in hand what is required to meet the end is right administration.

Keywords: Problem Facing By Women, Schemes, Statergies

Introduction

The term 'women's empowerment' means many people, depending on their ideological position and their flexible notions about a woman's position in society. For example, though right-wing politicians also now speak about women's empowerment, which helps them to take their own decisions by breaking all personal limitation of the society and family.

As this example shows, an understanding of 'women's empowerment' is clouded by the lack of ability to differentiate between sex and gender roles. Sex or biological roles mark the fundamental differences between women and men. Gender or social roles are especially variable and are firm by social, economic, political and cultural forces.

Objectives

- To study the challenges of women
- To discuss the government schemes and strategies' for women

Status of Women

In ancient to modern period Indian women were treated as the second gender. During the Moguls rule, the Indian women went through a sudden fall in the noble position. Education for women was stopped, and it lead to victims of evil practices like early child marriage. The Purdah system came into existence. Some social scientists have described the Mogul era as the dark age of women. The offensive acts like female infanticide had to be perform for self-preservation, and even a marriage had to be celebrated secretly to

prevent the abduction of a new bride. But the worst scenario was about to emerge, Indian women's position in society further deteriorated during the medieval period when Sati, child marriages and banned widow remarriage became part of social life in some communities in India. Among the Rajputs of Rajasthan, the Jauhar was practised. In Modern period some parts of India, the Devadasis or temple women were sexually exploited. Polygamy was widely practiced, especially among Hindu Kshatriya rulers. In many Muslim families, women were not allowed to Zenana areas of the house. Then Britishers arrived in India they observed to the social evils against women and watched to the wise counsel of social reformers like Raja Ram Mohan Roy and Swami Dayanand. They enacted several laws to improve the position of women, to bring back the dignity and glory of women. Some of these enactments were:

1. The Act of Prohibiting the practice of Sati (in 1850)
2. Cast disabilities removal act, 1850
3. The Hindu widow remarriage act, 1856
4. The special marriage act III of 1872
5. The Married Women's Property act, 1874
6. The child marriage act, 1872
7. The Hindu gains of earning act, 1930
8. The Hindu women's right to property Act, 1937
9. The Christian marriage act, 1872
10. The Parsee marriage and divorce act, 1936
11. The dissolution of the Muslim marriage act, 1939

These acts in themselves were excellent but, since these not reach to the society, because they were only on paper and not reflected in the actual society. But these acts gave a spark, and a chance to social reformers and social workers like Ishwar Chandra Vidya Sagar, Ranade, and Annie Besant. The status of women starts from this period.

Challenges for Women in India

Indian Women faced many challenges in their life. Targeting these issues directly affected the empowerment of women in India. So first let us know the issues of women .and study the schemes and strategies for women empowerment in India.

Education

Since independence the educational gap between women and men is severe. In comparison to 82.14% of adult educated men, only 65.46% of adult literate women are there in India. We should eradicate this educational gap and educate all women to attain their real place in the world It will break the wall of intolerance, negligence and exploitation

Poverty

Due to poverty, women are exploited as domestic helps. Women incomes are usurped by the man of the house. If poverty were not a concern, then the girl child will be able to follow her dreams without concerns about sexual exploitation, domestic abuse and no education or work. So we have to give more attention to improve their economic power.

Health and Safety

The health and safety concerns of women are important factors in gauging the empowerment of women in a country. However, there are alarming concerns where maternal healthcare is concerned. The empowerment of women begins with a guarantee of their health and safety. There are a number of schemes running under the women empowerment mission and we will discuss some of the major schemes are here:

The Mother and Child Tracking System

The Mother and Child Tracking System was launched in 2009; it monitors the health care system of mothers and their children have access to a collection of services, including pregnancy care, medical care during delivery, and immunization etc.,

Indira Gandhi Matritva Sahyog Yojana (IGMSY), Conditional Maternity Benefit (CMB)

Indira Gandhi Matritva Sahyog Yojana (IGMSY), Conditional Maternity Benefit (CMB) is a scheme sponsored by the national government. It is for pregnant and lactating women age 19 and used for their first two live births. The programme, which began in October 2010, provides money to ensure the good health and nutrition of the recipients. From March 2013 the programme is being offered in 53 districts around the country.

The Rajiv Gandhi Scheme for Empowerment of Adolescent Girls – Sabla

The Rajiv Gandhi Scheme for Empowerment of Adolescent Girls – Sabla launched in 2012 that targets adolescent girls. The scheme offers a package of benefits to at-risk girls between the ages of 10 and 19. It is being offered initially as a pilot programme in 200 districts. The programme offers a variety of services to help young women become self-reliant, including nutritional supplementation and education, health education and services, and life skills and vocational training.

Rashtriya Mahila Kosh

Rashtriya Mahila Kosh (The National Credit Fund for Women) was created by the Government of India in 1993. This scheme provides loans for lower-income women to begin small businesses Priyadarshini.

Priyadarshini, initiated in April 2011, is a programme that offers women in seven districts access, especially to self-help groups.

Rajiv Gandhi National Creche Scheme

This scheme is very essential for working women. Working women needs support regarding excellence, replacement and care for their young children while they are at work. This scheme provides nursery school and day care facilities. This scheme comes under the central social welfare board.

Short Stay Home For Women and Girls(SSH)

Under this scheme, it provides strength to the homeless girls. Short Stay Home for women and girls was introduced as a social defence mechanism, by the Department of Social Welfare in 1969. The scheme is meant to provide temporary lodging maintenance and rehabilitative services to women, and girls rendered homeless due to family discord, crime, violence, mental stress, social ostracism or are being forced into prostitution.

Conclusion

The above schemes are indirectly influencing the women workers and their economic condition. These schemes give stress on the individual training and entrepreneurship. They also employ the people through various means. So these schemes provide supplements and food items to women, hence playing a prominent role in women empowerment.

References

- Neera Desai, 'Changing Status of Women, Policies and Programmes' in Amit Kumar Gupta (ed) Women and Society, Development Perspective, Criterion Publishers, New Delhi. 1986.
- Kitchlu T.N., 'Women rights, Legislative Measures' in Yojana, Nov. 15, 1991, vol. 35, No. 20, Publication Division, Government of India, New Delhi.
- Neera Desai and Maithreyi Krishna Raj, Women and Society in India Op.cit, p. 44.
- Anil Kumar Gupta, (ed) Women and Society: The Developmental Perspective.
- Government of India, "Towards Equality" Report of the Committee on the Status of Women in India, 1975.